

Triple System Estimation of National Population Counts Through Log-linear and Latent Class Modeling

Daniel Weinberg¹ Tom Mule¹
daniel.weinberg@census.gov

¹U.S. Census Bureau

Abstract

The Continuous Count Study (CCS) is an important research effort within the Census Bureau to generate lower-level geographic and demographic estimates throughout the decade. One part of the study involves the use of administrative records to generate these estimates. The Demographic Frame is a comprehensive database of person-level data containing demographic characteristics and addresses associated with each person. Its information is derived from administrative, third-party, decennial census, and survey data sources. Prior modeling work has focused on predicting the probability that a given individual is found at a particular address on Census Day. This research will examine a triple-system estimation of person counts where the three systems are: 2020 Census, 2020 American Community Survey (ACS), and administrative records. We follow the ideas of van der Heijden et al. (2022), who estimated populations in New Zealand where individuals may be found on any number of lists, including being missing from all lists. We will be making use of the R package *cvam* (Schafer, 2021) to fit the models, including a latent class model to assign demographic information, which could differ among lists.

Disclaimer

Any views expressed on statistical methodology, technical or operational issues are those of the authors and not those of the U.S. Census Bureau. All data are approved for release under DRB approval number CBDRB-FY24-0409.

1 Introduction

The accurate estimation of population counts is a key objective in demographic research, particularly for generating lower-level geographic and demographic estimates during intercensal periods. The Population Estimates Program (PEP) currently produces population estimates down to the county level, but more

granular data would be beneficial. The Continuous Count Study (CCS) addresses this need within the Census Bureau, combining survey data, administrative records, and third-party information. One critical component of the CCS involves the use of the Demographic Frame, a comprehensive database containing person-level demographic information and associated addresses. This study explores a novel triple-system estimation (TSE) method for improving person counts by leveraging multiple data sources.

In Zaslavsky and Wolfgang (1993), the authors perform TSE using Census, a coverage survey, and administrative data. Their approach involved a cluster area survey, whereas we utilize a list sample. We build on the work of van der Heijden et al. (2022), who applied TSE to estimate populations in New Zealand, accounting for individuals present on any number of lists, including those missing from all lists. We will apply a similar methodology to U.S. data, focusing on three key data sources: the 2020 Census, the 2020 American Community Survey (ACS), and a particular vintage of the Demographic Frame.

2 Background

The datasets used in this study include the 2020 Census, the 2020 American Community Survey (ACS), and the 2020 vintage of the Demographic Frame (DF). To link individuals across these datasets, we use the Protected Identification Key (PIK), a unique identifier that enables consistent identification of people in different databases. One important requirement is that each individual must be associated with an address valid for ACS sampling to ensure the integrity of the analysis. The input to our model consists of the counts of individuals cross-classified by their presence in each of these databases, along with their reported Hispanic origin in each source. This cross-classification forms the basis for the log-linear and latent class models we use to estimate population counts and account for inconsistencies in demographic data across the datasets.

The Decennial U.S. Census is conducted every 10 years to count all residents of the United States, as required by Article I, Section 2 of the Constitution. The information gathered determines the number of seats each state holds in the U.S. House of Representatives and plays a key role in allocating hundreds of billions of dollars in federal funding to local communities.

The American Community Survey (ACS) is a yearly survey conducted by the U.S. Census Bureau that provides detailed demographic, social, economic, and housing data. Unlike the decennial census, which aims to count every person in the United States, the ACS collects data from a sample of households. The ACS provides timely and detailed information about the US population that is used to distribute funds, inform public policy, and to evaluate federal programs (U.S. Census Bureau, 2017).

The Demographic Frame is a critical component of the Census Bureau's Frames Program, serving as an extensive composite database of person-level information (Ortman, 2024). It integrates data from multiple sources, including administrative records and third-party data, to create a comprehensive dataset.

This database contains both demographic characteristics and associated address information for each individual, making it a powerful tool for demographic research and population estimation. The DF can be linked with other enterprise frames within the Census Bureau, enabling the integration of diverse data sources for more accurate analyses. Access to the DF is restricted, with availability limited to approved internal users who operate within a secure computing environment, ensuring the confidentiality and security of the data.

The R package *cvam* (Coarsened Variable Modeling), developed by Joe Schafer at the Census Bureau, is designed to fit log-linear models to multi-way contingency tables, with specialized capabilities for handling coarsened or missing values, including latent class models (Schafer, 2021). In our research, we leverage *cvam* in two key ways. First, we fit a log-linear model to estimate the cross-classification of individuals by Hispanic origin across multiple databases, providing a detailed assessment of the data. Second, we build on these results by fitting a latent class model, treating Hispanic origin in each database as an imperfect measure of the true Hispanic status. This approach helps account for inconsistencies across data sources, leading to more accurate population estimates.

3 Methodology

As input to the log-linear model, we require counts of individuals cross-classified by the databases in which they are found and Hispanic origin within each database. Missing values have all been filled in with imputed values. For records that were found in the ACS, we weight the counts using the sampling weights. For records not found in the ACS, we can obtain counts through subtraction, as shown in the diagram. For example, if we wish to find the count of records found in the Census and DF but not in the ACS, we subtract the number of records found in all three databases from the number of records found in both the Census and DF.

Table 1: Diagram showing how initial data were obtained. Teal cells were sample-weighted, gray cells were known, and yellow cells were computed through subtraction.

		ACS		
DemoFrame	Census	Yes	No	Total
Yes	Yes			
	No			
No	Yes			
	No		unobserved	
Total	Total			

Once we've obtained this table, we input it to *cvam*. We specify the model to incorporate main effects, two-way interactions between the presence within

the databases and Hispanic origin for each database, as well as three-way interactions between the values across different datasets. However, one limitation is that interactions between the presence and value within a given database cannot be modeled. If we define presence within the three databases using the binary variables A, B , and C and the binary measure of Hispanic origin within the databases as X_A, X_B , and X_C , then the model would be specified in the language of cvam as

$$X_A * X_B * X_C + A * X_B + A * X_C + B * X_A + B * X_C + C * X_A + C * X_B + A * B + A * C + B * C \quad (1)$$

where the $*$ symbol here indicates an interaction, as well as the inclusion of all lower order terms. For example, $A * X_B$ includes not only the interaction between presence in database A and the covariate value in database B, but also the corresponding main effects of A and X_B .

The model is fit using the Expectation-Maximization (EM) algorithm, which alternates between fitting the model and proportionally distributing the known totals based on the model’s estimates. This iterative process allows the model to estimate counts for the “hidden cells,” which represent individuals not found in any of the three databases. Ultimately, the model outputs fitted counts for $2^6 = 64$ cells, which correspond to the three databases and the three possible values of Hispanic origin.

Since Hispanic origin can differ across databases, we desire to ascertain a “true” Hispanic origin for each individual. One simple way to accomplish this task is to take its value in each database as the truth in turn.

The cvam package provides functionality for fitting latent class models, which we use to analyze Hispanic origin across three databases. Specifically, we input a contingency table of counts corresponding to 8 cells, derived from the cross-classification of Hispanic origin in the three datasets. In this model, Hispanic origin is treated as a latent variable that is unobserved for all records. The model assumes conditional independence of the observed Hispanic origin across databases, given the underlying latent factor. The outputs of the model include the latent class probabilities, $P(L = 0), P(L = 1)$, where L is the latent factor, as well as the conditional probabilities, $P(X_i|L), i \in \{A, B, C\}$.

To account for sampling uncertainty inherent in the ACS, we fit the model 80 times using ACS replicates, which are a set of 80 estimates designed to measure the uncertainty introduced by the ACS’s complex survey design (U.S. Census Bureau, 2010). The 90% margin of error for our estimates is obtained from the formula

$$\text{MOE} = 1.645 \times \text{SE} \quad (2)$$

where

$$\text{SE} = \sqrt{\frac{4}{80} \sum_{r=1}^{80} (\theta_r - \theta_0)^2}. \quad (3)$$

Here, θ_r is one of the 80 replicate estimates and θ_0 is the estimate based on the full sample weight.

4 Results

The model is fit using the EM algorithm. The procedure alternates between fitting the model and dividing up the known totals in proportion to the model fit. After `cvam`'s fitting routine converges, we obtain the 64 fitted counts corresponding to the 3 databases and the 3 values of Hispanic origin. To resolve the inconsistencies in Hispanic origin across databases, we can utilize one of the database's values as the truth. Table 2 shows the Hispanic origin counts when each of the three databases is used as the truth. We note that there is little difference between the Census and ACS truth. However, the Hispanic count is a bit lower for the DF truth, while the non-Hispanic count is higher. Total population is constant across methods.

Table 2: National population counts of Hispanic origin based on status in each of the three databases. Total population is fixed for all methods. Totals may differ due to rounding rules.

	Census Truth	DF Truth	ACS Truth
Hispanic	61,920,000	61,580,000	61,880,000
Non-Hispanic	254,800,000	255,100,000	254,800,000
Totals	316,720,000		

Once the log-linear model is fit, the results can be distilled into $2^3 = 8$ counts representing all combinations of Hispanic origin in the three databases. We then create a binary latent variable L that represents the “true” Hispanic origin. We assume that Hispanic origin in each database is independent given the latent class. The model's parameters are then fit using `cvam`'s `cvamEstimate` function. Because the latent class is unlabeled, we assume that the smallest class corresponds to the Hispanic class.

Table 3 shows these results. The proportion of Hispanics (0.1957) is higher than the released proportion of 0.187 (U.S. Census Bureau, 2021). Overall, we see that Hispanic origin in the Census agrees quite well with the Hispanic latent class. Hispanic origin in the Demographic Frame agrees less often, while Hispanic origin in the ACS agree the least of the three databases.

Finally, we multiply the class proportion estimate with the total population estimate to obtain final estimates of the Hispanic/non-Hispanic populations. Specifically, we multiply the Hispanic population proportion, given as 0.1957 in Table 3, by the total population, given as 316,720,000. We also compute 90% margins of error by running the entire process 80 more times with the different ACS replicate values. We then obtain the θ_r values, which are needed for Eqs. (2)-(3). Table 4 contains these results.

Table 3: Estimates derived from latent class modeling.

P(Hispanic Latent Class)	0.1957
P(Hispanic in Census Hispanic Latent Class)	0.9953
P(Non-Hispanic in Census Non-Hispanic Latent Class)	0.9991
P(Hispanic in DemoFrame Hispanic Latent Class)	0.9788
P(Non-Hispanic in DemoFrame Non-Hispanic Latent Class)	0.9964
P(Hispanic in ACS Hispanic Latent Class)	0.9475
P(Non-Hispanic in ACS Non-Hispanic Latent Class)	0.9876

Table 4: Estimates of the total Hispanic/non-Hispanic populations utilizing the class proportions and the total population from the previous tables. The MOEs are computed with the 80 ACS replicates.

	Estimate	90% MOE
Hispanic	61,990,000	67,670
Non-Hispanic	254,700,000	103,100
Total	316,720,000	155,200

5 Limitations and Future Directions

There are several limitations to the datasets used in this study. First, the 2020 ACS interviews were interrupted due to the COVID-19 pandemic, potentially leading to gaps or inconsistencies in the data collected that year. Additionally, individuals included in the analysis must have a PIK, which requires linking to either the Social Security Numident or an Individual Taxpayer Identification Number record. This reliance on PIKs could exclude individuals who lack these identifiers, such as certain undocumented populations. Furthermore, all addresses associated with individuals must be linked to the Master Address File (MAF), and only those addresses considered valid for ACS sampling are included in the study. These constraints lead to an undercount of the 2020 population, which was 331,449,281 (U.S. Census Bureau, 2024).

Future directions for this research include several key enhancements. One area of focus is obtaining counts for individuals at non-ACS valid addresses by using a two-system estimation approach with the Census and Demographic Frame databases, which could provide a more comprehensive view of the population. Additionally, similar analyses can be performed throughout the decade by integrating data from the ACS, the Demographic Frame, and a third-party database, allowing for continuous improvement in population estimates. Another direction is extending the current methodology to attributes with more than two values, such as race or age categories, which would offer a more detailed understanding of demographic patterns and further refine the accuracy of population counts across diverse groups.

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